

Customer Satisfaction in Connection with Online Trading with Specific Reference to Amazon in Banashankari Vicinity Bangalore City

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Pradeep, G., et al.
“Customer Satisfaction in Connection with Online Trading with Specific Reference to Amazon in Banashankari Vicinity Bangalore City.”
Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 118–27.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575311>

Dr. G. Pradeep

*Associate Professor, Department of PG Studies
Jain College PG Centre, V.V Puram, Bangalore*

R. Supriya

Student 1st M.Com, Jain College, PG Centre, VV Puram, Bangalore

R. Karthik

Student 1st SEM M.Com., Jain College, PG Centre, VV Puram, Bangalore

Introduction

Customer satisfactions a key and value outcome of good marketing practices. According to Drucker (1954) the principle purpose of a business is to create satisfied customers. Increasing customer’s satisfaction has been found to lead to higher future profitability, lower cost related defective goods and services, increased buyer willingness to pay price premiums, provide, referrals and use more of the product, and higher levels of customer retention and loyalty. Increasing loyalty, in turn, has been found to lead to increase in future revenue and to reduction in the cost of future transactions.

According to estimation the cost of attracting the more customers is five to seven times greater than the cost of retaining and established customer. Customer satisfaction is a key factor/experts even argue that it is more important than price in determining whether the customer is willing to return to a business after his or her initial experience and whether the customer will be in claim to recommend the business to others.

Online trading is simply buying and selling assets through a brokerage’s internet-based proprietary trading platforms the use of online trading increase dramatically in the mid/to late nineties with the introduction of affordable high-speed computers and internet connections.

Online trading is the act of purchasing and selling products only through internet. The trader buys and sells using an online trading platform.

Amazon was founded by “JEFF BEZOS” on July 5th 1994 in BELLEVUE Washington it has been situated in Three locations in India (Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai). It is an American based multinational electronic commerce company

Amazon was founded in the garage of ‘BEZOS’ rented home in Bellevue ‘Washington’ BEZOS Parents invested \$250000 in the start up in July 1995, company began service as an online book store in October 1995, the company announce itself to the Public.

Amazon products:Echo & Alexa, Fire TV Stick, Kindle E-Readers & e-books, Amazon prime video, Amazon prime music,Mobiles, Computers, TV, Appliances, Electronics, Men’s fashion, Women’s Fashion, Home, Kitchen, Pet caring products, Furniture, Grocery & Household supplies, Sports, fitness, Bags , Luggage, Toys, Baby products, Kid’s fashion, Car, Motorbike, Industrial goods, Books & Bill payments, Flight tickets, Gift cards, Art, Handicraft, Collectibles.

Definition

According to “Philip Kotler” person’s feeling of pleasure or disappointment which resulted from comparing the products perceived performance or outcome against his or her expectations

Statement of Problem

Research was scarce in the field of customer satisfaction in connection with online purchase of goods covering under the broad umbrella of e-commerce from the review of literatures cited and hence it is evident that no solid research has taken place in the above mentioned topic and that paved the path to undertake this particular research with reference to Amazon Banashankari area.

Research gap

From the above statement of the problem it has given clarity to take up research in the customer satisfaction with connection to online trading with reference to Amazon in Banashankari vicinity in Bangalore.

Objectives

1. In order to assess the customer satisfaction levels in Amazon.
2. To assess the factors which are contributing towards the customer satisfaction in Amazon.
3. To dig out the factors if any which is contributing towards the dissatisfaction levels of customers in Amazon.

Limitations of the Study

1. Time constraint.
2. Place constraint.
3. The research is confined only to Amazon only in Banashankari area.

Research Design

1. Data type: Primary Data
2. Method of sampling: Simple Random sampling is the method of sample selection which gives each possible sample combination.
3. Sample size: 80 samples
4. Sampling technique: Direct questionnaire method
5. Data type: Both qualitative and quantitative data used in this survey.
6. Statistical tools: Pie charts and bar diagrams
7. Mathematical tools: Percentages
8. Research type: Empirical research

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Pie chart showing the gender of respondents

1) Gender

● M
● F

Interpretation for the above diagram

From the above diagram it can be inferred that out of the total respondents of 80, 54% of them are female respondents and remaining 46% of them are male respondents, this shows that the male respondents are less than female respondents.

Pie chart showing the marital status of respondents

2) Marital status

● Married
● Single

Interpretation of marital status

From the above pie chart, it can be inferred that respondents are up to 18% who are unmarried and 82% of them are married.

Pie chart showing the age group of respondents

Age group

● 18 to 25
● 25 to 40
● 40 to 55
● Above 55

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it can be inferred that age group of 18 to 25 (82%), 25 to 40 (12%), 40 to 55 (4%) respectively. This shows age group of 18 to 25 respondents are more transacting through online in Amazon app.

Pie chart showing the occupation of respondents

Occupation

● Student
● Business man
● Government employee
● Private employee

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents out of 100% students 71%, Business man 4% Government employees 0%, Private employees 25% this shows that students are using Amazon website to purchase the products 20.

Pie chart showing the Income of respondents.

Income

Interpretation

From the above inferred that income less than 20000 are of 66%, 20000 to 40000 are of 21%, 40000 to 60000 are of 10%, above 60000 3% this shows that income of below 20000 are using online trading through Amazon website.

Pie chart showing the number of people utilizing and purchasing the product in Amazon.

How long you are using the product and shopping by Amazon?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that Amazon website has been used to purchase products through online less than 1year 37%, 1 year 17%, more than 1 year 46% respectively this shows that people are using Amazon website more than 1 year.

Pie chart showing the duration of people spending on online shopping.

How much time you spend on online shopping?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents purchase goods weekly once (22%) once a month (30%), Twice a month (12%), every 2or 3 months (36%) respectively. It shows that respondents are buying the product once in two months.

Bar chart showing reasons for preferring Amazon app for shopping.

What are the main reasons you preferred Amazon for shopping?

Interpretation

From the above bar graph, it is inferred that respondents shopping in Amazon for less price 29%, Good quality 31%, fast delivery 10%, Standard 4%, More options 26% respectively. This shows that respondents are using Amazon website to purchase their products for good quality goods and variety of products.

Pie chart showing money spent to shop in Amazon

How much you can spend for shopping on Amazon?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, inferred that respondents are spending their money from 500 to 1000 (46%), 1000 to 1500 (29%), 1500 to 2000 (8%), above 2000 (17%) respectively. More respondents are spending only of 500 to 1000rs to purchase their product in Amazon website.

Pie chart showing various schemes attracts customers towards Amazon.

Are you shopping with based on?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents are shopping for discount and offers 53%, Fast delivery 15%, Product quality 26%, Fair deal 7% respectively. Respondents are using Amazon websites for only discounts and offers from them.

Pie chart showing mode of payment of respondents.

What is the mode of payment you usually preferred the most?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents will prefer Credit card 9%, Debit card 17%, Net banking 11%, Cash on delivery 63% respectively. Respondents are purchasing product from mode of cash on delivery.

Pie chart showing reason for choosing online shopping instead of offline shopping.

Why you are choosing online shopping instead of offline shopping?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred respondents are using online shopping because to save time 55%, Wide choices 16%, Ease to find product 29% respectively. Respondents are transacting through online to save time.

Pie chart showing the factor influence to purchase product in Amazon.

What are the sources which make you purchased product from Amazon?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that family and friends 63%, online advertisements 22%, transactions security 5%, Advertisement (Print & broadcast) 10% respectively. This shows that only the family and friends are using Amazon website to purchase goods or products.

Pie chart showing the evaluation of price constraint while shopping through Amazon.

The price is matter when you shopping from Amazon?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents strongly agree 28%, Agree 59%, strongly disagree 0%, disagree 13% respectively. Most of the respondents agree that they purchase goods only for price in Amazon website.

Pie chart showing returns and exchange policy.

Amazon had a reasonable return and exchange policy?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, inferred that respondents strongly agree 20%, Agree 57%, strongly disagree 4%, Disagree 19% respectively. Respondents will trusted Amazon written and exchange policies.

Pie chart showing regular customers of Amazon shopping app.

Instead of other shopping application, you are able to retain as regular customer of Amazon?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that strongly agree 13%, Agree 61%, strongly disagree 4%, Disagree 22% respectively. Respondents are willing to remain as Amazon customers may be for good quality of goods.

Pie chart showing analysis of information gathered based on below mentioned criteria.

How do you choose online shopping site?

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that respondents are choosing online shopping to purchase their by referred by friends 25%, Online reviews 44%, Advertisements 12%, Based on offers 19% respectively this shows that respondents are more influenced by reviews to purchase their products through online.

Bar graph showing type of product purchased by respondents.

What kind of products do you buy?

Interpretation

From the above bar graph, it is inferred that respondents buy grocery of 27%, Accessories 57%, Cosmetics 19%, Apparels 20% respectively. This shows that Amazon website has excelled in selling more of accessories than the other products.

Bar graph showing how often people purchase products in Amazon

On which occasions do you make purchase?

Interpretation

From the above bar graph, it is inferred that respondents purchase product for festival 39%, to gift 15%, Weddings 3%, others 55% respectively. This shows that purchase their product in other occasion other than seasonal times.

Bar graph showing kind of problem that arise while purchasing online shopping.

What kind of problems did you face while doing online shopping?

Interpretation

From the above bar graph, it is inferred that respondents try to step back to purchase product because delay in delivery 30%, Product damage 25%, Cheap Quality of product 40%, non-delivery 5% respectively. This shows that Amazon should improve quality of goods.

Pie chart showing Amazon order tracking.

Amazon order tracking?

- Simple
- Complex

Interpretation

From the above pie chart, it is inferred that 91% respondents are saying it is simple to track their products where it is arriving and 9% respondents are saying it is rigid this shows that purchasing product in Amazon website is easy.

Findings

- In order to achieve customer satisfaction, Amazon should improvise on providing good quality products and deliver the products at the earliest.
- Customers are willing to purchase their products in Amazon website because of discount and offers on products it should be maintained in same way.
- In Banashankari area most of customers will purchase only accessories. Amazon should try to give wide choices of accessories so that they would refer others to buy the products in Amazon.
- Customers are dissatisfied because there are no wide choices in products delay in delivery and some of the product's quality is not good.

Conclusion

This study concluded online shopping is a highly best one, when compared to other shopping. The study about the various aspects of customer satisfaction on online shopping is satisfied. The research conducted helps to make identification over its strength and weakness of online shopping.

Bibliography

1. <https://www.freshworks.com>
2. <https://www.iforex.in/getting-started>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Customer_service

Questionnaires

Customer satisfaction in connection with online trading with specific reference to Amazon in Banashankari vicinity Bangalore city.

- 1) Name:
- 2) Gender
 - Male
 - Female
- 3) marital status
 - married
 - single
- 4) Age group
 - 18 to 25
 - 25 to 40
 - 40 to 55
 - Above 55

- 5) Occupation
 - Student
 - Business man
 - Government employee
 - Private employee
- 6) Income
 - Less than 20000
 - 20000 to 40000
 - 40000 to 60000
 - Above 60000
- 7) How long you are using the product and shopping by Amazon
 - Less than 1 month
 - Less than 1 year
 - 1 year
 - More than 1 year
- 8) How much time you spend on online shopping?
 - Weekly once
 - Once a month
 - Twice a months
 - Every 2 or 3 months
- 9) What are the main reasons you preferred Amazon for shopping?
 - Less price
 - Good quality
 - Fast delivery
 - Standard
 - More options
- 10) How much you can spend for shopping on Amazon?
 - 500 -1000
 - 1000 - 1500
 - 1500 – 2000
 - Above 2000
- 11) Are you shopping with based on?
 - Discount & offers
 - Fast delivery
 - Product quality
 - Fair deal
- 12) What is the mode of payment you usually preferred the most?
 - Credit card
 - Debit card
 - Net banking
 - Cash on delivery
- 13) Why you are choosing online shopping instead of offline shopping?
 - Save time
 - Wide choices
 - Ease to find product
- 14) What are the sources which make you purchased product from Amazon?
 - Family and friends

- Online advertisements
 - Transactions security
 - Advertisement(print & broad cast)
- 15) The price matter when you shopping from Amazon?
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
- 16) Amazon had a reasonable return and exchange policy?
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
- 17) Instead of other shopping application you are able to retain or regular customer of Amazon?
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
- 18) How do you choose online shopping site?
- Referred by friends
 - Online reviews
 - Advertisements
 - Based on offers
- 19) What kind of products do you buy?
- Grocery
 - Accessories
 - Cosmetics
 - Apparels
- 20) On which occasions do you make purchase?
- Festival
 - To gift
 - Weddings
 - Others
- 21) What kind of problems did you face while doing online shopping?
- Delay In delivery
 - Product damage
 - Cheap quality of product
 - Non – delivery
- 22) Amazon order tracking?
- Simple
 - Complex